

EFFECT OF WINTER WHEAT IRRIGATION ON ITS GROWTH AND YIELD.

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Annotation: This article discusses the cultivation of the Starshina variety of winter wheat in the meadows of the Bukhara region, characterized by alluvial, medium salinity, and medium sand soils. The wheat is fertilized with N250, P175, K90 kg/ha, and soil moisture is maintained at 70-80-70% of the field's marginal moisture capacity before irrigation. The irrigation is carried out using a 2-3-1 system, with 6 applications totaling 737-842 m³/ha per irrigation and 4622 m³/ha seasonally. This cultivation method resulted in a yield of 63.8 c/ha of winter wheat, with a profitability level of 19.1%, and a total water usage of 726 m³/ha.

Key words: water-saving technologies, salinity, winter wheat, irrigation standards, moisture regimes, starshina variety, feeding rate, yield, economic efficiency.

Preface.

Scientists worldwide are conducting research in priority areas aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of water scarcity, promoting the widespread adoption of water-saving technologies, enhancing the reclamation of saline lands, and ensuring stable, high yields of agricultural crops. Enhancing the efficiency of water-saving irrigation technologies under conditions of water scarcity, achieving consistent high yields in agriculture, improving the reclamation of saline soils, optimizing soil water-physical properties and salt regimes, and increasing productivity represent promising directions for future research.

Research method and experimental system:

Experimental research was conducted to determine the optimal irrigation procedure for the Starshina variety of winter wheat in the Bukhara region. The experimental fields, located within the territory of Raboti Kalmoq MFY, Bukhara district, Bukhara region, have moderately saline, meadow-alluvial soils with sizot waters settling at depths of 1.5-2.0 meters. The mineralization level ranges from 2.0 to 4.0 g/l. The study was carried out between 2002 and 2005 on medium sand soils based on their mechanical composition. During the research, experimental options for watering the Starshina variety of winter wheat were tested in a single layer with three repetitions.

Table 1

The experimental system for the development of watering supply of winter wheat is the conditions of saline soils.

Options	Random soil moisture, the chawning field is relative to the moist container %	The amount of nutrients	Irrigation standards, m ³ /ha
1 (control)	Ratic dimensions	N-250; P-175; K-90 kg/ha	Ratic dimensions
2	70-70-65		On moisture deficit in the 0-70 cm layer of soil
3	70-75-70		
4	70-80-70		

Scientific research was carried out in the field of saline soils of Bukhara region on the basis of PSUEAITI research methods to determine the regulations of the starshine of the winter wheat. (table 1).

Experimental results:

From 2002 to 2005, research was conducted on experimental farms at the Bukhara Regional Research Institute in the Bukhara Region, focusing on the conditions of saline soils prevalent in the area. The study investigated the nutrient requirements for winter wheat cultivation, particularly the application of ore-based fertilizers tailored to the region. Specifically, phosphorus was applied at 175 kg/ha and potassium at 90 kg/ha, as per the recommended norms.

During the study, the full norm of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers, along with the preparation of the land in the fall, was applied for the cultivation of winter wheat. Additionally, 30% of the nitrogen fertilizers were applied before planting the seeds, another portion during seed sowing in the autumn, and the final application during the tillering stage.

After selecting the experiment for winter wheat cultivation from 2002 to 2005, the land was plowed and leveled longitudinally and transversely twice, utilizing "Dlinnobaz". This process involved cutting the higher parts of the soil and filling in the deeper areas. Following land preparation, the experimental area was fully irrigated with 680 m³ of water in early September. Phosphorus fertilizers at 100% and 30%, along with 30% of nitrogen fertilizers (100 kg in total), were incorporated into the soil and treated twice. On the 1st of October, 250 kg of seeds were planted per hectare using a seeding machine.

To ensure soil moisture and seed production during sowing, 700-750 m³ of water per hectare was applied annually for seed germination. The watering norms for winter wheat were determined using the formulas developed by S.N. Rajov.

From 2002 to 2005, as per the first option of the research, the irrigation amount ranged from 1,635 to 934 m³/ha, with a seasonal irrigation total of 5,348 m³/ha. During the scientific investigation, irrigation norms were set at 4,886 m³/ha. Seasonal irrigation rates, based on the autumn soil moisture content, were approximately 70-70-65% of the total water requirement. Consequently, the deficit in water availability was relatively low, at 461 m³/ha.

In the third version, the irrigation limits for winter wheat, based on the soil moisture content of 70-75-70%, ranged from 807.3 to 1064.7 m³/ha, with a seasonal irrigation rate of 4724 m³. Irrigation standards for autumn wheat, set at 40-80-70% of field capacity, amounted to 737-842 m³. These standards were applied along with N-250, P-175, K-90 kg fertilizers. The seasonal irrigation rate for this setup was 4622 m³/ha, with a deficit of less than 726 m³/ha compared to the control option.

Figure 1. Seasonal irrigation norms during the winter wheat for 2002-2005.

The initial irrigation for winter wheat occurs during the early stages of plant growth. In spring, the first irrigation is conducted during the wheat's growth cycle, specifically during the waxing phase.

In the control group, irrigation scheduling for autumn wheat under saline soil conditions resulted in an average grain yield of 55.9 tons per hectare over three years. In version 2, the grain yield of autumn wheat over the same period

increased to an average of 59.7 tons per hectare, representing an improvement of 4.2 tons per hectare.

The grain yield of winter wheat over three years in the third version of the research reached 68 tons per hectare. This represents an increase of 4.9 tons per hectare compared to the autumn harvest grown under economic conditions. During the study, grain yields under the 70-80-70% watering regime for autumn wheat ranged from 63.6 to 74.2 tons per hectare, with an average of 63.8 tons per hectare over three years. This marks an improvement of 7.9 tons per hectare compared to the control option.

During the study, it was observed that the winter wheat growth in the high-norm version resulted in taller plants, but with fewer tillers compared to other options. Consequently, due to the higher moisture levels, there was a reduction in the spacing between the plants, resulting in smaller grains in the ears. This decrease in grain number per plant led to lower yields. Conversely, in regions with adequate moisture, there was an increase in productivity when plants were grown under normal irrigation conditions.

In the conditions of saline soils of the Bukhara region, the autumn wheat yields a border of 63.8 tons per hectare due to the 70-80-70% water moisture content.

Figure 2. Impact of the order of watering winter wheat.

Conclusions

1. In the meadows of the Bukhara region, the Starshina variety of winter wheat is cultivated in moderately saline, medium sandy soil. It is fertilized with

N250, P175, and K90 kg/ha, maintaining a moisture level at 70-80-70% of field capacity. The irrigation norms consist of six cycles with a volume ranging from 737 to 842 m³ per hectare, totaling 4622 m³ for the season. These irrigation practices ensure a profitability level of 19.1% with a yield ranging from 63.8 centners per hectare and result in water savings of 726 m³.

2. In the meadow of Bukhara region, in conditions of alluvial, moderately saline, medium sandy soils, the Starshina variety of winter wheat is fed at the rate of N250, R175, K90 kg/ha, and the soil moisture before irrigation is maintained at 70-80-70% compared to the marginal field moisture capacity. the protein content is 15.2%, the gluten content is 28.5%, and the protein content is 0.7% higher and the gluten content is 1.2% higher than the control version.

3. In the moderately saline, medium sand soils of the Bukhara region, the planting period for the Starshina variety of winter wheat is from October 10 to October 20. When the feeding regime consists of N-250, P-175, K-90 kg/ha, the development phases of the winter wheat plant result in a yield 8.0-14.2 c/ha higher than the control, totaling 61.2 c/ha.

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